

Decision to Purchase Hand Sanitizer During Covid-19

Yulianingsih¹, Rachmat Gunawan², Muhammad Anjah Nurulloh^{3*},
Danu Suryani⁴

Faculty of Economics, Universitas Djuanda

Corresponding Author: Muhammad Anjah Nurulloh

muhammad.anjah2019@unida.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Product Quality,
Price, Brand Image, Purchase
Decision

Received : 8, May

Revised : 22, June

Accepted: 24, July

©2023 Yulianingsih, Gunawan,
Nurulloh, Suryani: This is an open-
access article distributed under the terms
of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0
Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

Hand sanitizer is one of the people's choices in preventing the transmission of Covid-19. The high demand for hand sanitizers is a business opportunity for hand sanitizer entrepreneurs in developing their businesses. The aim of this study; 1) to find out consumer responses regarding product quality, price, brand image and purchasing decisions; 2), to analyze the effect of product quality, price and brand image simultaneously and partially on the decision to purchase hand sanitizer at PT Gamajaya Global Grosir. The method used is multiple linear regression analysis with a total sample of 100 consumers. The results showed that 1) consumer responses regarding product quality, price, brand image and purchasing decisions were in good criteria; 2) product quality, price and brand image simultaneously and partially have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions on PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's hand sanitizer

INTRODUCTION

Hand Sanitizer is a liquid for cleaning hands which has the advantage of being anti-bacterial. The high public demand for hand sanitizers during the Covid-19 period is a business opportunity for hand sanitizer entrepreneurs in developing their businesses. The accuracy of choosing a marketing strategy will provide support to influence consumers in making purchasing decisions

PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is a distributor of medical devices (ALKES). One of the products being marketed is a hand sanitizer. The average achievement of the revenue target from sales of hand sanitizers in 2020 only reached 88.7%. Revenue realization reached the target in 2020, only in June, amounting to 106.8%, this was due to increased consumer demand due to an increase in the COVID 19 virus. The next revenue target was achieved in October, namely 114.2% and in November that is equal to 101.4% this happened because of a sales promotion by giving a 10% discount. Whereas for other months the revenue target was not achieved due to changes in purchasing decisions allegedly due to product quality, price, and brand image which were still considered unfavorable by consumers.

Every company definitely wants to provide the best products for consumers so that their products have advantages compared to competing products, but the hand sanitizer marketed by PT. It turns out that Gamajaya Global Grosir is still considered not to meet consumer expectations. This is because there are still products that are returned (return) to the company. The reason consumers returned the product was that the hand sanitizer liquid changed color, the packaging was leaking, damaged and dented. The number of products returned is still within acceptable limits, namely 31 bottles, but if this continues to occur, it is possible that the number of product returns will increase, so the company needs to correct these errors and be more careful so that mistakes do not occur. as complained by consumers.

In making purchasing decisions, of course, consumers will determine price comparisons with similar products. According to Kotler and Keller (2016: 132) price is one of the factors evaluated by consumers to make purchasing decisions. To find out price comparisons with similar products from competing brands, price observations are carried out. Based on the results of observations, it is known that competing brands offer hand sanitizers at lower prices. In this case, consumers will certainly make product choices at lower prices as a comparison in the evaluation process to make purchasing decisions. This price difference is thought to have resulted in a decrease in purchasing decisions for PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale.

Brands chosen by consumers can be said to have a good brand image. Products with a good brand image can form a strong brand platform capable of expanding brand existence in competition for a long time. The brand is the public perception of the company or its products. To find out the cause of the change in purchase decision which is allegedly caused by brand image, a preliminary survey was conducted of 30 (thirty) consumers who bought hand sanitizers at PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale. A preliminary survey was conducted at malls,

agents and markets, in the South Jakarta area. This preliminary survey was conducted for 4 days on January 15-18, 2022, based on the results of the survey that consumers still consider the brand image of hand sanitizers to be unfavorable.

Based on these problems, a study was conducted with the title "The Influence of Product Quality, Price, and Brand Image on Hand Sanitizer Purchasing Decisions at PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Tjiptono (2016: 130). Product quality is a consumer's perception of the overall quality or superiority of a product or service according to the expectations desired by the consumer. Product quality indicators are (1) performance; (2) additional features or characteristics (features); (3) reliability; (4) compliance with specifications (confirmation to specification); (5) durability; (6) serviceability; (7) aesthetics; (8) perceived quality (perceived quality).

Price is the exchange rate for a product or service. Tjiptono (2016: 218) states that price is the only element of the marketing mix that generates income or income for the company. Price indicators are (1) price suitability; (2) conformity of price with product quality; (3) price compatibility with benefits; (4) price competitiveness.

Firmansyah (2019: 60), brand image (brand image) is a perception that arises in the minds of consumers when remembering a brand of a particular product Brand image indicators, namely (1) the image of the maker; (2) user image; (3) Product image.

Kotler and Keller (2018: 188). Purchasing decision is a study of how consumers form preferences between brands in choosing, buying and using, how these products can satisfy consumer needs and wants. Purchasing decision indicators are (1) product choice; (2) brand choice; (3) dealer choice; (4) purchase amount; (5) purchase timing; (6) payment methods.

Previous Research

1. Rifki, M et al (2023)
2. Hidayat, G. G et al (2022)
3. Rachmah, F. N et al (2022)
4. Putianugra and Sulyanto (2022)
5. Yulianingsih, et al (2020)

←.....

Figure 1. Frame Of Mind

METHODS

The objects in this study consist of independent variables, namely product quality (X1), price (X2), and brand image (X3), while the dependent variable is the purchase decision (Y). The data source of this research comes from primary and secondary data.

The type of research is descriptive and verification. Primary data was obtained from the results of processed questionnaires, while secondary data was obtained from reading literature, books, articles related to the research topic. The study population consisted of 4,878 people. Using the Taro Yamane formula, a sample of 100 people was obtained with a leeway for uncertainty with an error rate of 10%. The sampling technique used uses the incidental sampling method, namely sampling by chance by taking respondents who happen to be in a place that fits the research context.

Data analysis methods were carried out by validity test, reliability test, classic assumption test (normality test, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity), -t test, F test, coefficient of determination, multiple correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis.

RESULTS

The result of the validity and reliability tests for the variables of product quality, price, brand image and purchasing decisions show that all statement items are declared valid and reliable.

Before the multiple linear regression method is used in hypothesis testing, the model will first be tested whether the method meets the classical assumptions or not. The classic assumption consists of the normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test. Following are the result of the normality test with a histogram graph which gives a normal distribution pattern with a symmetrical bell-like shape.

Figure 2. Normality Test Result with Histogram Graph
Source: Primary Data Processed, 2022

In this study, there was no problem of multicollinearity due to the value of $VIF < 10$ and the tolerance value of more than 0.5. Here is the table of multicollinearity test results:

Table 1. Multicollinearity Test Results Coefficients

Type	Collinearity Statistics		Decision
	Tolerance	VIF	
Product Quality (X_1)	.503	1.989	Multicollinearity-Free
Price (X_2)	.805	1.243	Multicollinearity-Free
Brand Image (X_3)	.558	1.793	Multicollinearity-Free

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2022

The results of the heteroskedasticity test show that the points formed on the scatterplot graph do not form a clear pool and spread above below the number 0 Y axis, so there can be no heteroskedasticity problems in this test. The following is a picture of the heteroskedasticity test results with a scatterplot graph:

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test Results
Source: Data Processed, 2022

Table 2. Recapitulation of Respondent Characteristics

No	Characteristic	Characteristics of Respondents	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender	Woman	55	55
2.	Age	>30	30	30
3.	Recent Education	High School / Vocational School	41	41
4.	Income	IDR 2.6- IDR 3 million	38	38

5.	Work	Private Employees	43	43
----	------	-------------------	----	----

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 2 it can be seen that the majority of respondents are women with a total of 55 people or 55%, dominated by age is > 30 years with a total of 33 people or 30% with their last education, namely SMA / SMK with 41 respondents or 41%, with an average income of Rp. 2.6 - Rp. 3 million as many as 38 people or 48%.

Here is a recapitulation of employee responses to product quality, price, brand image and purchasing decisions.

Table 3. Recapitulation of Respondents' Assessment of Product Quality (X_1)

No	Description	Value	Categories	Interpretation
1	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> can clean hands from germs effectively.	3.94	Good	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> sold by PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir contains ethanol ingredients can clean hands from germs effectively.
2	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> has good materials.	3,78	Good	This PT Gamajaya Global Grosir hand sanitizer has good ingredients according to the standard composition of <i>the handsanitizer</i> set by WHO such as 96% ethanol, 98% gtliserol, 3% hydrogen peroxide and sterile water or aquadest.
3	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> contains extra skin moisturizer so it does not cause irritation.	3,88	Good	This PT Gamajaya Global Grosir <i>hand sanitizer</i> contains extra skin moisturizer that is medical standard so that it does not cause irritation and does not cause a dry feeling on the skin.
4	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> has a distinctive comfortable aroma.	4.02	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> has a soothing aroma so that consumers will remember it only by its aroma.
5	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> easily seeps into	3,94	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> easily absorbs into the pores of the hands well so it is comfortable when used daily. This is proven because this <i>hand sanitizer</i> has a skin

	the pores of the hands			care component that facilitates penetration into the pores of the hand.
6	The texture of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> is not sticky	4,16	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> has a soft texture so it does not cause stickiness because it has a formula that dries quickly without leaving a sticky feeling on the hands.
7	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> meets established medical standards	3,62	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> meets the established standards such as being registered with BPOM and is in accordance with the established composition so that it is safe for daily use.
8	The content of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> is in accordance with the information provided on the packaging.	3,57	Good	The content in <i>h</i> and <i>sanitizer</i> is good as stated on the packaging, namely ethanol-based liquids that have been tested microbiologically and dermatologically for hand hygiene with medical standards accompanied by skin care components.
9	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> can work for up to five minutes	3,36	Enough Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> is good enough to last up to five minutes, so the evaluation for the company to make the <i>h</i> <i>andsanitizer</i> stronger for a long time.
10	<i>Expired Hand sanitizer</i> PT Gamajaya Global Grosir long enough	3.67	Good	<i>The expired hand sanitizer</i> of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir is quite long until it reaches three years from manufacture because it has an ethanol content of more than 60%. But if the packaging has been opened, the ethanol content will decrease due to evaporation.
11	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> is comfortable to use	3,66	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> is comfortable to use such as not sticking to hands, practical packaging and has a skin care formula that adds to the attractiveness of buyers.
12	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i>	3.73	Good	The company serves consumer complaints submitted through <i>online</i> applications

	provides fast complaint handling			
13	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> has an appeal to the packaging provided	3,68	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> packaging is good so that it can give a positive impression that is different from other products and adds a distinctive characteristic, namely having a <i>pocket</i> shape so as to make its own attractiveness for consumers.
14	The color of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer packaging</i> is the attraction	3,67	Good	The color of the packaging <i>hand sanitizer</i> of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir is well because it has a unique <i>packaging</i> color, which is red and white like the Indonesian flag so that it becomes an attraction for consumers.
15	The quality of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> is in accordance with consumer wishes	3,82	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> is good as desired, which is comfortable to use, has its own advantages such as having a medical-standard skin care formula and properly sterilizing hands.
16	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> has its own advantages over similar products	3,96	Good	This PT Gamajaya Global Grosir <i>hand sanitizer</i> has more advantages than similar products such as it can last up to five minutes, smells soothing, does not make the skin dry and is not sticky.
	Average	3,78	Good	Respondents' assessment of the quality of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> products is considered good because it is considered quite effective in cleaning hands, does not cause irritation, has a distinctive aroma, is not sticky and is safe for daily use.

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 3, the recapitulation results stated that respondents' responses to product quality had an average assessment value of 3.78 with a good category. In the statement of the texture of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's non-sticky hand sanitizer has the highest value of 4.16 with a good category and PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's hand sanitizer statement can work for up to five

minutes has the lowest value of 3.36 with a fairly good category. Product quality is one of the things that need to be considered by business actors, some ways that business actors can do to improve product quality are by promoting, developing products (variations), identifying opportunities and threats and identifying the advantages and weaknesses of products.

Table 4. Recapitulation of Consumer Valuations of Price (X_2)

No	Description	Value	Categories	Interpretation
1	The price of the products offered is affordable for respondents	3,68	Good	<i>Hand sanitizers</i> are affordable according to consumer finances. This is because the company's target market is sufficient with the price offered.
2	The price of <i>hand sanitizer</i> offered is quite cheap with respondents' finances	3,76	Good	The hand sanitizer offered is cheap so that respondents can choose from the price variants offered because this <i>hand sanitizer</i> has three sizes, namely 40 ml, 60 ml and 100 ml so that consumers can adjust the choice of products that are considered affordable enough with their finances.
3	The price of the product is sufficient with the quality offered.	3,74	Good	The price offered to consumers is good in accordance with the quality offered, which can sterilize hands effectively, easily seep into the pores of the hands and has a medical standard skin care formula.
4	Costs incurred in accordance with the quality received	3,88	Good	The costs incurred are good in accordance with the quality received because the quality received is better and has more benefits than similar products.
5	Product prices can compete with similar products	3,78	Good	<i>Hand sanitizers</i> vary depending on size. however PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir can buy at a more affordable price PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir provides a price comparison feature that consumers can use to directly find the cheapest price offers from all e-commerce in Indonesia.
6	The price of the product is cheaper compared to	3,54	Good	The price of the product is cheaper than similar products because the company offers the best quality

	similar products.			products at relatively affordable prices.
7	Price products according to benefits	3.62	Good	The price of PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> is good in accordance with the benefits received, which is effective in eradicating bacteria and viruses. This hand sanitizer is suitable for consumers who do not like fragrances, because this <i>hand sanitizer</i> is a disinfectant liquid only.
8	<i>Hand sanitizers</i> have greater benefits.	3,54	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizer</i> has greater benefits compared to other products. As it can last up to five minutes and has a skin care formula.
	<i>Average</i>	3.69	Good	The price of <i>hand sanitizers</i> can vary from each manufacturer, even though the raw materials clearly follow the standards set by WHO, PT. Gamaja Global Grosir has a very cheap price than other similar products

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 4 related to the recapitulation of price variables, it can be seen that the cost statement issued in accordance with the quality received has the highest value of 3.88, while the lowest value is contained in the product price statement is cheaper than similar products and in the hand sanitizer statement has a greater benefit of 3.54 which according to respondents the price set by the company is not in accordance with the benefits expected by consumers. This can be used as an evaluation by the company so that the company can set the right and appropriate price. The price is not too expensive but with the many benefits obtained, it is certainly the hope of respondents, by providing benefits for buyers, also providing comfort. The average score for the statement on the price indicator is 3.69, meaning that the price set by PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is affordable and in accordance with what the company provides, be it affordability, people's purchasing power, quality, and benefits.

Table 5. Recapitulation of Respondents' Assessment of Brand Image (X_3)

No	Description	Value	Categories	Interpretation
1	The <i>Hand sanitizer</i> brand is made by a company that	3.31	Enough	Brand <i>hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale. Made by companies that have high credibility, especially in the health sector. This is proven because this

	has high credibility.			<i>hand sanitizer</i> is often used by medical personnel in hospitals.
2	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> brand is made by companies that are considered in the field of health products	3.40	Enough	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale is quite well considered in the business world because it develops in the health sector
3	Feel safe using <i>hand sanitizer</i> from PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale.	3.96	Good	This <i>hand sanitizer</i> product in the eyes of respondents has a special feature because it does not make the skin of the hands dry.
4	Feels more sterile when used.	3.82	Good	Respondents felt more sterile when using <i>hand sanitizer</i> . Because this <i>hand sanitizer</i> has a brand that has been trusted by medical personnel in hospitals.
5	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is a trusted brand.	4.19	Good	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale. It is trusted for respondents because it has <i>pocket-shaped</i> packaging, product safety and neat packaging.
6	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir has a positive image in the community.	3.88	Good	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale. Having a positive image in society is said to be good. Because it can help people to sterilize hands so that viruses or germs are not easily attached and of course health becomes more awake.
	<i>Average</i>	3.76	Good	The brand image on <i>hand sanitizer</i> is said to be good. This is because <i>hand sanitizers</i> are trusted, consumers feel safe and proud when consumers, and products have a good reputation image among the public.

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 5 recapitulation of respondents' responses to brand image on hand sanitizers at PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir received an average score of 3.76 included in the good category. The highest interpretation number is 4.19 with the statement that hand sanitizer products are trusted brands. belongs to

the good category. While the lowest interpretation number is 3.31 with hand sanitizer brand statements made by companies that have high credibility.

Table 6. Recapitulation of Respondents' Assessment of Purchasing Decision (Y)

No	Description	Value	Categories	Interpretation
1	Brand <i>hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is the first priority in buying <i>hand sanitizer</i>	3.78	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's hand sanitizer has become a priority for respondents in buying <i>hand sanitizers</i> . Because this hand sanitizer is included in the ninth best <i>hand sanitizer</i> order. This certainly needs to be improved by the company so that this <i>hand sanitizer</i> product is more of a top priority.
2	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir has more advantages when compared to other brands	4.00	Good	PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's hand sanitizer has more advantages than other <i>hand sanitizer</i> products. Like having a formula with medical-standard skin care components.
3	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is the best <i>hand sanitizer</i> brand from other competitors	4.19	Good	This PT Gamajaya Global Grosir hand sanitizer has a good brand image because it is included in the order of the best hand sanitizer, so consumers make purchasing decisions on this <i>hand sanitizer</i> .
4	<i>Hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is the best <i>hand sanitizer</i> brand from other competitors.	3.86	Good	The best PT Gamajaya Global Grosir <i>hand sanitizer</i> expanding market share can be said to enlarge the business because if the market share increases, then of course demand will increase, then the number of products produced must also increase, including production power will increase
5	PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir has respondents who decide to buy products here rather than anywhere else	4.03	Good	Respondents who have bought products here because respondents believe the products sold are original products and and the company is well known as a company engaged in health.
6	Name of <i>hand sanitizer</i> shop PT. Gamajaya Global	3.88	Good	Respondents feel thatPT Gamajaya Global Grosir's hand sanitizer shop is easy to find in the <i>current market</i>

	Grosir is easy to find in the <i>market place</i> .			<i>place</i> , because by writing down the wholesale <i>hand sanitizer</i> has appeared.
7	Respondents decided to buy <i>hand sanitizer</i> at PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale	3.34	Enough	Respondents make purchases on PT Gamajaya Global Grosir's <i>hand sanitizers</i> when needed, therefore companies must be more aggressive in promoting <i>hand sanitizers</i> so that they become respondents' needs.
8	Respondents bought <i>hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale according to the required amount, which is more than one.	3.82	Good	Respondents making more than one purchase is good, because at the time of the pandemic they are required to use <i>hand sanitizers</i> so that respondents make purchases of more than one product.
9	Respondents purchased <i>hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale on a regular basis.	3.35	Enough	Respondents purchase PT Gamajaya Global Grosir <i>hand sanitizers</i> regularly because respondents have trusted the products sold by the company so this is certainly very good for the company.
10	Respondents purchased <i>hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale when needed.	3.31	Enough	Respondents purchase PT Gamajaya Global Grosir <i>hand sanitizer</i> when needed, that is, respondents will buy this <i>hand sanitizer</i> if their stock has run out.
11	Respondents made payment for <i>hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale in cash.	3.96	Good	Respondents feel good about cash payments, so when respondents place orders <i>online</i> , respondents do not need to think about non-cash payments.
12	Respondents made payment for <i>hand sanitizer</i> PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale on a non-cash basis.	4.03	Good	Respondents feel that the cashless payment method is good for respondents to make payments via <i>transfer</i> .
	Average	3.79	Good	The buyer chooses the product of PT. Gamaja Global Wholesale

				because they need and love <i>hand sanitizer</i> products
--	--	--	--	---

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 6, the recapitulation results stated that respondents' responses to purchasing decisions had an average assessment value of 3.79 with a good category. In the statement of buying hand sanitizer, PT Gamajaya Global

Type	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	7.180	4.018		3.787	,001
Product Quality	.510	.084	.613	6.044	,000
Price	.304	.094	.388	3.103	,000
Brand Image	.255	.197	.376	3.785	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision (Y)

Grosir because it has a good brand image has the highest value of 4.19 with a good category and the respondent's statement of buying hand sanitizer when needed has the lowest value of 3.31 with a good category. Product quality, price and brand image are one of the things that need to be considered by the company, some ways that companies can do to improve product quality price and brand image are by promoting, conducting product development (variations), identifying opportunities and threats and identifying product advantages and weaknesses.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The results of multiple linear regression analysis are in the following table:

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results
Coefficients

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 7, a regression equation with the following estimation model is obtained:

$$Y = 7,180 + 0.510X_1 + 0.304X_2 + 0.355X_3 + \epsilon$$

The results can be interpreted as follows:

1. The constant value obtained is 7,180 which means product quality (X1), price (X2) and brand image (X3) = 0 then the purchase decision (Y) of PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale has a positive value.
2. Product quality regression coefficient (X1) which is positive (0.510), which means that every time there is an increase in product quality (X1), it will be followed by a purchase decision (Y) for PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale assuming variable price (X2) and brand image (X3) are fixed. Quality of hand sanitizer products PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is good because it uses a medical-standard composition that does not cause dry hand skin.
3. The price regression coefficient (X2) is positive (0.304) which means that every increase (suitability) in the price (X2) will be followed by an increase in the purchase decision (Y) of PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale assuming the

variables of product quality (X1) and brand image (X3) remain. Price of hand sanitizer products PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is relatively affordable because it has prices that match the benefits received.

- The brand image regression coefficient (X3) is positive (0.255) which means that every time there is an increase in brand image (X3), it will be followed by an increase in purchasing decisions (Y) for PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale assuming the variables of product quality (X1) and price (X2) are fixed. A good brand image will make consumers believe in a product. Brand image of hand sanitizer PT. Gamajaya Global Grosir is trustworthy, easy to find on social media and easy to remember.

Multiple Correlation Analysis

The following are the results of the correlation analysis test

Table 8. Results of Multiple Correlation Coefficient Analysis *Model Summary*

Type	R	R Square	Adjust Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.729 ^a	.532	.517		3.303
Predictors: (Constant), Product Quality, Price and Brand Image					

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Based on Table 8, an R value or correlation of 0.729 is obtained which shows that the correlation number of 0.729 is in a strong category, so product quality, price, and brand image to purchasing decisions have a strong relationship. This means that the more product quality, price suitability, and good brand image, the purchase decision will increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on Table 8, the R Square value is 0.532 or 53.2%. This shows that the percentage of influence of Product Quality, Price, and Brand Image variables on purchasing decisions is 53.2%. While the remaining 43.2% was influenced by variables that were not included in this research model. According to Kotler and Keller (2018: 166), purchasing decisions are influenced by other factors such as cultural factors, social factors and personal factors.

Hypothesis Testing

1. F Test

The results of simultaneous testing can be seen in the Variance Analysis table (ANOVA) with the help of the SPSS program as follows:

Table 9. Simultaneous Regression Testing

ANOVA ^a						
	Type	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1190.091	3	396.697	36.347	.001 ^b
	Residuals	1047.749	96	10.914		
	Total	2237.840	99			
a. Dependent Variable: purchasing decision						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Product quality, Price, Brand image						

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 9 the F_{calculate} value is 36,347 and the F_{table} value for $\alpha = 0.1$ with degrees of freedom $V1=3-1=2$ and $V2=100-2-1= 97$ of 2.14 where it can be seen that F_{calculate} is greater than F_{table} ($63,895 > 2.14$) it can be concluded that H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that with a 90% confidence level the independent variables Product quality, price and brand image have a positive and significant effect together (simultaneously) on the decision to purchase hand sanitizer at PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale.

2. Test t

Here is a partial test recapitulation of product quality (X1), price (X2) and brand image (X3):

Table 10. Recapitulation of Partial Testing (Test t)

Variable	t _{count}	t _{table}	Criterion	Conclusion
Product quality	6.044	1,290	t _{calculate} > t _{table}	Positive and significant influence
Price	3.103	1,290	t _{calculate} > t _{table}	Positive and significant influence
Brand image	3.785	1,290	t _{calculate} > t _{table}	Positive and significant influence

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 10, it is obtained that the most dominant Product Quality variable influences the decision to purchase hand sanitizers at PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale. This is because the quality of the product has the highest calculation and exceeds the table and is supported by a probability value that is smaller than the standard probability value. The smaller the probability value obtained, the more significant the effect on the quality of hand sanitizer products at PT. Gamajaya Global Wholesale.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Consumer responses regarding product quality are included in the high category, consumer responses regarding prices are included in the high category and consumer responses regarding brand image are included in the high category

2. Product quality, price and brand image partially and simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.

The suggestions from the author are as follows:

1. Increases durability when used so that this product will be more superior than other products.
2. The company is making efforts to improve prices by providing sales promotions, for example buying in large quantities will be given a 10% discount.
3. Improving the company's reputation in the eyes of consumers by improving the quality of packaging, changing the size of the composition text to make it larger, conducting ongoing advertising and promotion campaigns, working with influencers.
4. Increasing the time of purchase such as timed promos or so-called flash sales.
5. For further research other variables can be added such as location, promotion, consumer trust, distribution channels and others.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research is still needed on the topic of decision to purchase hand sanitizer during covid-19.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank all parties who have helped the author both in academic and non-academic.

REFERENCES

- Alma, Buchari. 2018. *Manajemen Pemasaran dan Pemasaran Jasa*. Alfabeta, Bandung.
- Firmansyah. (2019). *Pemasaran Produk dan Merek : Planning dan Strategi*. Qiara Media.
- Hidayat, G. G., Samsuri, & Yulianingsih. (2022). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Harga dan Promosi Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Pada PT Mustika Citra Rasa Holland Bakery Bogor. *Karimah Tauhid*, 1(4), 422-431.
- Kotler, Philip and Kevin Lane Keller. (2018). *Marketing Management*, 15th edition. Pearson Education. Inc.
- Rachmah, F. N., Andari, T. T., & Yulianingsih. (2022). Pengaruh Brand Awareness, Perceived Quality Dan Brand Loyalty Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Ban Hankook Pada PT. Budiyanto Semesta Grup Di Cikarang Kabupaten Bekasi. *Karimah Tauhid*, 1(6), 767-776.
- Rifki, M., Gunawan, R., & Yulianingsih . (2023). Pengaruh Persepsi Harga Dan Citra Merek Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Flat Shoes. *Visionida*, 9(1), 84-95.
- Sugiyono. 2017. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. Alfabeta. Bandung.

- Tjiptono, Fandy. 2015. Strategi Pemasaran. CV Andi. Yogyakarta.
- _____ & Greforius Chandra. 2016. Pemasaran Jasa (Prinsip, Penerapan, dan Penelitian). CV Andi. Yogyakarta.
- Yulianingsih. (2018). Hubungan Antara Kualitas Produk Dan Citra Merek Dengan Keputusan Pembelian Pada PT. Hyundai Mobil Indonesia Cabang Serpong-Tangerang. *Visionda*, 4(2), 23-37.
- _____, Kartini, T., & Kurniawan, D. (2020). Analisis Keputusan Pembelian Melalui Citra Merek dan Persepsi Harga. *Inovator*, 9(1), 8-16.